

Creating mutations in the GS domain of Alk2

Goal: To create mutations in the GS domain of Alk2 to remove phosphorylatable serine residues

Mutations done using the Quickchange XL kit following kit instructions.

Template sequence:

Full length ACVR1A containing S187A and T189A mutations from previous mutagenesis experiments.

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ATGGTAGATGGAGTGATGATTCTTCCTGTGCTTATCATGATTGCTCTCCCCTCCCCTAGTATGGAAGATGAGAA
GCCCAAGTCAACCCCAAACCTCTACATGTGTGTGTGAAGGTCTCTCTGCGGTAATGAGGACCACTGTGAA
GGCCAGCAGTGCTTTTCCTCACTGAGCATCAACGATGGCTTCCACGTCTACCAGAAAGGCTGCTTCCAGGTTTA
TGAGCAGGGAAAGATGACCTGTAAGACCCCGCCGTCCCCTGGCCAAGCTGTGGAGTGCTGCCAAGGGGACT
GGTGTAAACAGGAACATCACGGCCAGCTGCCCACTAAAGGAAAATCCTTCCCTGGAACACAGAATTTCCACTT
GGAGGTTGGCCTCATTATTCTCTGTAGTGTTCGCAGTATGTCTTTTAGCCTGCCTGCTGGGAGTTGCTCTCC
GAAAATTTAAAAGGCGCAACCAAGAACGCCTCAATCCCCGAGACGTGGAGTATGGCACTATCGAAGGGCTCA
TCACCACCAATGTTGGAGACAGCACTTTAGCAGATTTATTGGATCATGCGTGTGCATCAGGAAGTGGCTCTGG
TCTTCCTTTTCTGGTACAAAGAACAGTGGCTCGCCAGATTACACTGTTGGAGTGTGTGCGGAAAGGCAGGTAT
GGTGAGGTGTGGAGGGGAGCTGGCAAGGGGAAAATGTTGCCGTGAAGATCTTCTCCTCCCGTGATGAGAA
GTCATGGTTCAGGGAAACGGAATTGTACAACACTGTGATGCTGAGGCATGAAAATATCTTAGGTTTCATTGCT
TCAGACATGACATCAAGACACTCCAGTACCCAGCTGTGGTTAATTTTCCATTATCATGAAATGGGATCGTTGTA
CGACTATCTTCAGCTTACTACTCTGGATACAGTTAGCTGCCTTCGAATAGTGCTGTCCATAGCTAGTGGTCTTG
CACATTTGCATAGAGATATTTGGGACCCAAGGGAAACCAGCCATTGCCCATCGAGATTTAAAGAGCAAAAA
TATTCTGGTTAAGAAGAATGGACAGTGTTCATAGCAGATTTGGGCCTGGCAGTCATGCATTCCAGAGCACC
AATCAGCTTGATGTGGGGAACAATCCCCGTGTGGGCACCAAGCGCTACATGGCCCCGAAGTTCTAGATGAA
ACCATCCAGGTGGATTGTTTCGATTCTTATAAAAAGGGTCGATATTTGGGCCTTTGGACTTGTGTTTGTGGGAAGT
GGCCAGGCGGATGGTGAGCAATGGTATAGTGGAGGATTACAAGCCACCGTTCTACGATGTGGTTCCCAATGA
CCCAAGTTTTGAAGATATGAGGAAGGTAGTCTGTGTGGATCAACAAAGGCCAAACATACCCAACAGATGGTT
CTCAGACCCGACATTAACCTCTCTGGCCAAGCTAATGAAAGAATGCTGGTATCAAATCCATCCGCAAGACTC
ACAGCACTGCGTATCAAAAAGACTTTGACCAAAATTGATAATTCCTCGACAAATTGAAAAGTACTGTTCCAG
TAAAGGTGGATACGGATCCGACTACAAGGATGACGATGACAAGTGA
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Primer sequences:

ACVR1S187AT189AS194Afor cagaaaaggaagaccagcgccacttcctgatgcac

ACVR1S187AT189AS194Arev gtgcatcaggaagtggcgctggtcttcctttctg

Introduces S194A mutation when ACVR1 S187A,T189A is used as template. Designed by Georgina Kerr.

Quickchange II XL SDM kit used from Agilent Technologies. Method followed as per kit instructions using a 9 minute extension time and 18 cycles. (Size of plasmid + insert = 8974bp)

PCR product frozen at -20C overnight

Plasmid treated for 1h at 37C with DPN1 and 1µl transformed into Bronze efficiency competent cells incubating for 30 minutes on ice before heat shocking for 45s at 42°C. Cells were rested on ice for a further two minutes before adding 500ul LB. Cells were grown for 2h at 37°C while shaking before spinning down for 5 minutes at 5000 rpm. Supernatant was poured off and pellet was resuspended in 100µl LB and plated onto LB Amp+ plates. Plates were grown overnight at 37°C and colonies were picked for sequencing.

Overnights were grown up in 10ml LB Amp+. Samples were spun down at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes and the DNA was extracted using a standard Quiagen Miniprep protocol.

Plasmid was frozen at -20C with sample sent for sequencing.

Sequencing:

Standard pcDNA3 vector sequencing primers in both forward and reverse direction were sent for sequencing at SourceBioscience. Results revealed all four colonies contained the required mutation and confirmed fidelity of the remainder of the construct.